
Discussion on Solutions of a Class of Cubic Diophantine Equations

Liu Zhiwei

College of Science, Hezhou University, Hezhou 542899, Guangxi, China

Abstract This paper uses the basic theory of Pell equation to discuss the following contents: hypothesizing $p = 3r^2 - 2$ or $3p = r^2 + 2$, and p is odd prime in the $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, r is positive integer, the cubic Diophantine equation $x^3 - 3py^2 = 1$ has no positive integer solution (x, y) ; when $p < 100$, the equation has positive integer solution (x, y) if $p = 37$.

Keywords Cubic Diophantine equation; Pell equation; Petrr group

Cubic Diophantine Equation

$$x^3 - 3py^2 = 1, x, y \in \mathbb{N}, p \text{ is an odd prime greater than } 3 \quad (1)$$

The solution of this equation has attracted public attention in number theory, since the literature [1] had proven: when $p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$, equation (1) has no solution (x, y) , hence it comes to the discussion about $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, which only some conclusions have been reached.

In this paper, the following results are discussed according to the basic properties of Pell equation:

Theorem If $p = 3r^2 - 2$, $r \in \mathbb{N}$ or $3p = r^2 + 2$ (2)

then equation (1) has no solution (x, y) .

In order to prove the theorem, this paper first proves the following conclusions.

Lemma 1 If (x, y) is a set of solutions to equation (1), thus,

$$x - 1 = 9q^2, x^2 + x + 1 = 3pb^2, y = 3ab, a, b \in \mathbb{N} \quad (3)$$

Demonstration Hypothesizing (x, y) is a set of solutions to equation (1), because $x^3 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ according to (1), then $x \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x^2 + x + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $\gcd(x^2 - 1, x^2 + x + 1) = 3$. Since p is an odd prime greater than 3, thus $x - 1 = 9pa^2$, $x^2 + x + 1 = 3b^2$ according to (1),

$$y = 3ab, a, b \in \mathbb{N} \quad (4)$$

Or (2). According to the literature [1], (4) is not valid.

Lemma 2 [2] Hypothesizing D is a given positive integer with no square factor, there exists a unique set of positive integer (D_1, D_2, λ) that satisfy

$$D_1 D_2 = D, \lambda \in \{1, 2\}, \gcd(D, \lambda) = 1, (D_1, D_2, \lambda) \neq (1, D, 1) \quad (5)$$

thus equation

$$D_1 u^2 - D_2 v^2 = \lambda, u, v \in \mathbb{N} \quad (6)$$

has a solution (u, v) .

For a given D , the group of positive integers defined by Lemma 2 is called the Petrr group of D , marked as $p(D)$.

Lemma 3 Hypothesizing D_1, D_2 are positive integer satisfy $D_1 > 1$, if equation

$$D_1 u^2 - D_2 v^2 = 1, u, v \in \mathbb{N} \quad (7)$$

has a solution (u, v) , then it must have a unique solution (u_1, v_1) that satisfy $u_1\sqrt{D_1} + v_1\sqrt{D_2} \leq u\sqrt{D_1} + v\sqrt{D_2}$, (u, v) is all the solutions to this equation.

(u_1, v_1) is called the smallest solution to the equation (7). Hence any set of solutions (u, v) to the equation can be expressed as

$$u\sqrt{D_1} + v\sqrt{D_2} = (u_1\sqrt{D_1} + v_1\sqrt{D_2})^k, k \in \mathbb{N} \quad (8)$$

Demonstration Refer to literature [3]

Lemma 4 If the solution (u, v) of equation (7) satisfies

$$u\sqrt{D_1} + v\sqrt{D_2} < (\sqrt{D_1} + \sqrt{D_2})^3 \quad (9)$$

Then (u, v) must be the smallest solution to the equation.

Demonstration According to the lemma 3: there exists positive odd number k which makes (u, v) satisfies (8).

Hypothesizing (u, v) is not the smallest solution of equation (7), then $k \geq 3$, according to (8),

$$u\sqrt{D_1} + v\sqrt{D_2} \geq (u_1\sqrt{D_1} + v_1\sqrt{D_2})^3 \geq (\sqrt{D_1} + \sqrt{D_2})^3 \quad (10)$$

is in contradiction with (9). Therefore, if (u, v) satisfies (9), then it must be the smallest solution of equation (7).

Lemma 5 Any set of solutions (u, v) to the equation (7) can satisfy u_1/u and v_1/v , and (u_1, v_1) is the smallest solution of the equation.

Demonstration According to the lemma 3: there exists positive odd number K which makes the equation (8) true, then,

$$u = u_1 \sum_{i=0}^{(k-1)/2} \binom{k}{2i} (D_1 u_1^2)^{\binom{k-1}{2}-i} (D_2 v_1^2)^i$$

$$v = v_1 \sum_{i=0}^{(k-1)/2} \binom{k}{2i+1} (D_1 u_1^2)^{\binom{k-1}{2}-i} (D_2 v_1^2)^i \quad (11)$$

u_1/u and v_1/v can be proven from (11).

Demonstration of lemma

Hypothesizing (x, y) is a set solution of equation (1), according to the lemma 1, there exists positive integer a and b which make x and y satisfy (3), then

$$p(2b)^2 - 3(a^2 + 1)^2 = 1 \quad (12)$$

when x is eliminated in (3).

From (12), equation

$$pu^2 - 3v^2 = 1, u, v \in \mathbb{N} \quad (13)$$

has solutions

$$(u, v) = (2b, 6a^2 + 1) \quad (14)$$

Hypothesizing $D = 3p$, since p is an odd prime greater than 3, therefore, D is a positive integer with no square factor. Since equation (12) has solutions, according to lemma 2, $p(D) = (p, 3, 1)$, thus,

$$3u^2 - pv^2 = 2, u, v \in \mathbb{N} \quad (15)$$

and

$$3pu^2 - v^2 = 2, u, v \in \mathbb{N} \quad (16)$$

have no solutions (x, y) .

If p satisfies (2), then equation (15) has solutions $(u, v) = (r, 1)$ Nevertheless, it can be told that from above: it is inapprehensible when equation (1) has solutions. Therefore, there must be no solution to equation (1) if p satisfies (2).

Similarly, if p satisfies $3p = r^2 + 2, r \in \mathbb{N}$, since equation (16) has solutions $(u, v) = (1, r)$, therefore, equation (1) has no solution.

Reference

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